

POLICY BRIEF

Social integration in the context of the new patterns of migration

Inta Mieriņa

UNIVERSITY OF LATVIA
**INSTITUTE OF
PHILOSOPHY
AND SOCIOLOGY**

Introduction

How to integrate migrants successfully has become a major policy challenge across Europe. Integration approaches vary from country to country, but integration policies typically focus on fixed groups of people trying to adapt to a more or less homogeneous local society. At the same time, migration patterns today are becoming increasingly mobile and transient, and host societies themselves increasingly heterogeneous (Grabowska-Lusinska 2013; Engbersen et al. 2013; Luthra et al. 2016; Shubin & Dickey 2013). Focusing on new forms of migration, the 2018–2021 study «Well-being and Integration in the Context of Liquid Migration», conducted by researchers at the University of Latvia, challenges existing concepts and sheds new light on the integration process and its outcomes, with a particular focus on the subjective experiences of migrants themselves in different areas of their lives: economic, health, psychological and social well-being. The study answers the question: what does an increasingly mobile, liquid migration practice mean for integration? To what extent are the familiar notions of integration and assimilation appropriate for an increasingly rootless and unpredictable group of migrants? Is gradual settling in a place a necessary condition for integration? And how valid is it to speak of simultaneous «integration» in several places and communities? The analysis is based on a comprehensive mixed-methods study of Latvian migrants, including a survey of 6,242 emigrants and in-depth interviews with members of the target group (see Mieriņa 2022; TBD; Goldmanis & Mieriņa 2021).

Integration and new forms of migration

In recent years, academic debates have heightened concerns that traditional approaches to interpreting and measuring integration are no longer able to adequately explain processes of inclusion in complex societies (Grzymala-Kazłowska & Phillimore, 2017). They were developed to explain adaptation processes in the context of 'traditional' migration, where migrants settle permanently in new countries of residence, and fail to account for the everyday experiences of a new type of migrants who do not settle in one place (unaffiliated migrants), who may have close ties to several countries (transnational migrants), or who move to highly diverse neighbourhoods where no group can be considered a

majority (Grzymala-Kazłowska, 2016; Grzymala-Kazłowska & Phillimore, 2017; Boccagni & Hondagneu-Sotelo, 2021; Crul, 2016; Shubin & Dickey, 2013; Levitt, 2001). The aim of this study was therefore to contribute to the theoretical debate on what integration means, as well as to provide practical recommendations for assessing and promoting integration in the new context.

Conclusions

Our study confirms that the conventional notions of integration and assimilation do indeed not adequately describe processes of inclusion in the new, dynamic migration context. Unaccompanied and transnational migrants do not interpret integration as a linear, gradual adaptation to a single host society. Instead, integration is mainly about practical inclusion, «fitting in», being able to «navigate the system», access the necessary resources and live comfortably in the host society.

Theories often cite relationships with the local community as a crucial condition for integration, but our research highlights that the nature of these relationships is also important: relationships with the local community can be good but superficial.

Our study also shows that, in terms of identity, for transnational and liquid migrants, their symbolic ties with their homeland take on a special significance, as they provide a necessary sense of stability in their uncertain and transient lives. At the same time, they do not interfere with their liquid lifestyle. Social inclusion, attachment to the current host country as 'home' as well as to its culture, usually takes place only when the heaviest 'anchors' (Grzymala-Kazłowska, 2016) are relocated there, e.g. the family also moves (or one is established). Most migrants remain poorly psychologically embedded in their current place of residence.

Compared to other migrant groups, those whose future plans are the most uncertain showed little interest in integrating, as they do not see any benefit from investing their efforts. Unaffiliated and transnational migrants expressed strong resistance to assimilation and wanted to preserve their identity and culture while respecting the culture of the host country.

Liquid and transnational migrants often end up in highly diverse cities or multicultural transnational collectives. In both cases, they lack opportunities to interact and absorb 'local' culture, traditions and language. In multicultural cities, it is easier for migrants to fit in or 'blend in', while still retaining

their culture, values and identity and feeling comfortable. Smaller and more homogeneous places, on the other hand, give migrants more opportunities to form (and sometimes even be expected to form) place-specific social ties and to integrate into the local community in the traditional sense of assimilation. In addition, the study shows that liquid and transnational migrants today are more likely to integrate into their professional environment among their peers than into wider society.

In general, the new type of migrant is best characterised by a strategy of marginalization (Berry 1992). This is mainly the result of insufficient time and vague plans for the future, which do not allow for immersion in the local culture and society, and do not make such action strategically valuable.

The conceptual model

Based on the answers given by the respondents, the study proposes a new conceptual framework reflecting the «depth and breadth» of integration, from functional adaptation to deep integration and from integration in narrow "bubbles" to integration into society as a whole.

Functional adaptation allows migrants to become functional elements of society as a social system. Migrants are structurally well integrated (Huddleston et al 2013), i.e. they are engaged in the labour market and/or education, have sufficient income and also contribute to society. They have sufficient information, good language skills and legal status to access the resources they need, and they 'navigate the system' well enough to fully meet their daily needs. They feel comfortable and are seen to be «fitting in» to society.

However, functional adaptation does not include a sense of psychological attachment, belonging and

identification with the host society, strong social ties with the local population, cultural adaptation or civic participation. These dimensions suggest a deeper integration, similar to traditional interpretations of integration that emphasise gradual adaptation to the host society or even assimilation (see Penninx & Garcés-Masareñas, 2016). Deep integration implies a more active involvement in the local community through friendship or family ties, learning the local language, a sense of belonging to the local community, interest and understanding of its culture, participation in its festivals and traditions, and civic engagement in local issues.

It should also be noted that deep integration is possible without giving up one's culture and identity, and this is often the case with transnational migrants. Deep integration is often the next stage in the adaptation process and requires time and motivation on the part of migrants, as well as openness on the part of the host society. This is most easily achieved in small and homogeneous, yet culturally open communities.

In particularly diverse cities, there are often no homogeneous communities in which to integrate, and even when there are, people tend to integrate in smaller 'bubbles'. Even in highly diverse cities it is possible to integrate into society as a whole, but this is more likely to take the form of functional adaptation than deep integration.

Alternatively, as our analysis shows, people often integrate into smaller bubbles of international work groups, academic campuses, ethnic communities or subcultures and have little contact with the «outside world», their own neighbourhoods, etc. Integration in bubbles and the lack of meaningful links with the host society can hinder integration into the wider society (Nannestad, Svendsen & Svendsen, 2008).

Figure 1. Analytical model

Recommendations

- The study confirms the premise that has recently also been increasingly voiced in foreign publications, that the **host society plays the most important role in fostering integration**. In order to avoid the isolation of migrants in professional, international or ethnic bubbles, it is **important to provide opportunities for meaningful contacts with the local community and to promote openness**. The bonds of friendship that develop can encourage migrants to become more deeply rooted in the host society.
- Secondly, the analysis clearly shows that **when the future of a migrant**, including the length and possibility of remaining in a given country, **is uncertain, the motivation to invest time and effort in integration is reduced**. It is therefore important on the part of the state to give migrants as much long-term certainty as possible and a more stable basis for planning their future whenever possible.
- Thirdly, **there is a need to review integration indicators traditionally used in international comparisons** (e.g. MIPEX) in the context of today's complex migration patterns. The findings call for

'more mobile thinking' (Shubin & Dickey, 2013) and a relationship-based, dynamic and transformative interpretation of integration that takes into account the unpredictable trajectories of mobility and integration and recognises the diverse needs of migrants.

- Fourth, it is **desirable that attempts to promote integration become more holistic, open and «migrant-centred»**. Rather than trying to squeeze migrants into a formally defined 'framework', it is necessary to listen to and take into account their different expectations, to help them experience their roots, to support their life strategies and to exploit the potential of international mobility. This is the only way to reduce the politicised nature of integration, the assimilationist orientation and the disconnection of integration indicators from the real experience of migrants.

- Finally, **the proposed conceptual model can help theorists to better illustrate contemporary migrants' adaptation processes** beyond the outdated and inappropriate narratives of 'assimilationism' and 'multiculturalism'.

Berry, J. W. (1992). Acculturation and adaptation in a new society. *International migration*, 30(1), 69–85.

Boccagni, P., & Hondagneu-Sotelo, P. (2021). Integration and the struggle to turn space into "our" place: Homemaking as a way beyond the stalemate of assimilationism vs transnationalism. *International Migration*. DOI: 10.1111/imig.12846.

Crul, M. (2016). Super-diversity vs. assimilation: how complex diversity in majority-minority cities challenges the assumptions of assimilation. *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 42(1), 54–68.

Engbersen, G., & Snel, E. (2013). Liquid migration. Dynamic and fluid patterns of post-accession migration flows. In I. Grabowska-Lusinska, B. Glorius, & A. Kuvik (Eds.), *Mobility in Transition: Migration Patterns after EU Enlargement* (pp. 21–40). Amsterdam Uni. Press.

Goldmanis, M. & Mierina, I. (2021). Exploring Well-Being and Social Integration in the Context of Liquid Migration. Survey methodology. <https://migracija.lv/pub/2021-Goldmanis-Mierina-Survey-methodology.pdf>

Grabowska-Lusinska, I. (2013). Anatomy of post-accession migration. How to measure 'liquidity' and other patterns of post-accession migration flows. In I. Grabowska-Lusinska, B. Glorius, & A. Kuvik (Eds.), *Mobility in Transition: Migration Patterns after EU Enlargement* (pp. 41–64). Amsterdam University Press.

Grzymala-Kazłowska, A. (2016). Social anchoring: Immigrant identity, security and integration reconnected? *Sociology*, 50(6), 1123–1139.

Grzymala-Kazłowska, A. & Phillimore, J. (2017). Introduction: rethinking integration. New perspectives on adaptation and settlement in the era of super-diversity. *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 44(2), 179–196.

Huddleston, T., Niessen, J., & Tjaden, J. D. (2013). Using EU indicators of immigrant integration. EUR-OP.

Levitt, P. (2001). Transnational migration: taking stock and future directions. *Global networks*, 1(3), 195–216.

Luthra, R., Platt, L., & Salamońska, J. (2016). Types of migration: The motivations, composition, and early integration patterns of "new migrants" in Europe. *International Migration Review*, 52(2), 368–403.

Mierina, I. (2022). Migrantu pašidentifikācija un integrācija mītnes zemēs. No I. Mierina (red.), *Latvijas emigrantu kopienas: labklājība un integrācija mūsdienu migrācijas kontekstā*. Rīga: LU Filozofijas un socioloģijas institūts.

Mierina, I. (TBD). Re-imagining 'integration' in the light of the new forms of mobility. Npublicēts manuskripts.

Nannestad, P., Lind Haase Svendsen, G., & Tinggaard Svendsen, G. (2008). Bridge over troubled water? Migration and social capital. *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 34(4), 607–631.

Penninx, R., & Garcés-Masareñas, B. (2016). The concept of integration as an analytical tool and as a policy concept. In Garcés-Masareñas B., Penninx R. (Eds.), *Integration processes and policies in Europe* (pp. 11–29). Springer, Cham.

Shubin, S., & Dickey, H. (2013). Integration and mobility of Eastern European migrants in Scotland. *Environment and Planning A: Economy and Space*, 45(12), 2959–2979.

About the project

This research is funded by the Latvian Council of Science, project «Exploring Well-Being and Social Integration in the Context of Liquid Migration: A Longitudinal Approach» (Izp-2018/1-0042)

Coordinated by: Institute of Philosophy and Sociology University of Latvia

Project director: Dr. Inta Mierina

Implementation period: 09/2018–12/2021

Contact information

E-mail: inta.mierina@lu.lv

Address: Kalpaka bulvāris 4

Rīga, LV-1050, Latvija

<https://migracija.lv>

Migrācija ⇄ LV

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.5921016](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5921016)

LU Filozofijas un socioloģijas institūts, 2021

This work is licensed under the [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)

Layout: Aleksandrs Aleksandrov

UNIVERSITY OF LATVIA
INSTITUTE OF
PHILOSOPHY
AND SOCIOLOGY